

Additional file 5: Figure S5. Assessment of optimal Donor-bead concentration. The ideal Donor-bead concentration was determined once simultaneously in a mix of Europium Acceptor bead coupled 11A5 antibody and Terbium Acceptor-bead coupled LB509 antibody. Arrows indicate optimal 4B12 concentrations for both Acceptor-bead variants. AU: arbitrary units